

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF POLY(1,4 BUTYLENE CARBONATE-CO-TEREPHTHALATE)/ORGANICALLY MODIFIED LAYERED DOUBLE HYDROXIDES NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Poly(1,4 butylene carbonate-co-terephthalate) (PBCT)/organically modified layered double hydroxide (m-LDH) nanocomposites were successfully synthesized with a solution blending method. PBCT, a semi-crystalline and biodegradable copolymer, had been synthesized via a two-step procedure using sodium hydroxide as a catalyst. In order to improve the compatibility with PBCT, the LDH was modified by the intercalation of octanoic acid and stearic acid into interlayer space using coprecipitation method (OA-LDH, SA-LDH), respectively. X-ray diffraction (XRD) revealed that the modification of LDH resulted in significantly increased of the interlayer distance. Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (FTIR) studies showed that m-LDH contained both functional groups of organical modifier and LDH. The diffraction peaks of PBCT/OA-LDH nanocomposites at lower angle were extremely weak and board, indicating that OA-LDH layers formed a mixed of intercalated and exfoliated conformation in nanocomposites. However, in PBCT/SA-LDH nanocomposites, SA-LDH layers were fully exfoliated. Isothermal crystallization behavior of neat PBCT and 1, 3, 5 wt% PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites were studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The n values of all nanocomposites are close to 2, suggesting that the growth of PBCT spherulite is a 2-dimensional structure. The half-time for crystallization of nanocomposites decreased with the OA-LDH content, indicating that filler acted as a heterogeneous point which caused an increase in the crystallization rate. Nevertheless, the result of nanocomposites with the SA-LDH content is the opposite to that of OA-LDH, owing to the huge size of stearic anion on the LDH surface served as a barrier to hinder the motion of polymer chain.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, polymer nanocomposites with inorganic nanofillers have attracted extensive attention, due to their outstanding gas barrier properties, thermal properties, flame retardant and crystallization properties compared to conventional composites. These improvements can be attributed to their homogeneous dispersion in polymer matrix, and a high volume fraction of the interfacial area between polymer matrix and inorganic nanofillers. Several studies have focused on the addition of an inorganic layered material, such as layered silicate and a layered double hydroxide (LDH), to polymers which substantially enhance the mechanical and crystallization properties after intercalation and exfoliation within the polymer structure [1, 2].

Layered double hydroxides (LDHs), also known as anionic clays, are a class of two-dimensional layered material with positively charged brucite-like hydroxide layers and exchangeable anions located in the interlayer gallery. However, the strong electrostatic interactions between the hydroxide layers and hydrophilic of LDHs cause the intercalation or exfoliation very difficult in polymer matrix. Therefore, the organic modification of LDH is the key factor in the fabrication of polymer/LDH nanocomposites [3].

In this work, biocompatible and nontoxic octanoic acid (OA) and stearic acid (SA) were used as organic modifiers to prepare modified LDH via the coprecipitation method. Meanwhile, a new biodegradable polymer PBCT had been synthesized by two-step procedures. The PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites were prepared by solution blending. The structures, dispersion and isothermal

crystallization behaviors of various PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites were discussed by XRD, TEM, FT-IR and DSC.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material

Dimethyl carbonate (DMC), 1,4 butanediol (BD), dimethyl terephthalate (DMT), $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and octanoic acid were purchased from Alfa Aesar, Stearic acid was purchased from J. T. Baker. All chemicals used as received without further purification.

2.2 Preparation of organically modified LDH (OA-LDH, SA-LDH) by coprecipitation

The nitrate solution was prepared by adding magnesium nitrate and aluminum nitrate into deionized water in the molar ratio of 2:1. The aqueous solution of OA and SA was slowly dropped into nitrate solution with constant stirring. Simultaneously, the pH was kept at 10 by the addition of sodium hydroxide solution. Subsequently, the mixture was heated to 80 °C and aged overnight with a nitrogen flow. Then, the precipitate was filtered, washed several times using deionized water and freeze dried.

2.3 Synthesis of poly(1,4 butylene carbonate-co-terephthalate) (PBCT)

PBCT was synthesized via a two-step procedure as described by Lee (2013) [4]. First, the monomers and catalyst were successively added into flask under nitrogen gas. Then, the flask was heated to 120 °C for 1 h, while distilling off the volatiles atmosphere. In the second step, the temperature was increased to 190 °C followed by step reducing pressure at 190 mmHg. Finally, the polycondensation was carried out at 210 °C under full vacuum. After the reaction, the copolymers were cooled to room temperature.

2.4 Preparation of PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites

The nanocomposites of PBCT with the desired amount of inorganic fillers were prepared by solution blending. A certain amount of OA-LDH and SA-LDH (1, 3 and 5 wt%) were separately dispersed in 10 mL chloroform at room temperature and stirred for 3 h. Then, the solutions were added to an earlier-prepared solution of PBCT dissolved in 20 mL chloroform and kept stirred for 3 day to fully intercalate PBCT into LDH layers. Then, the various concentrations of PBCT/m-LDH solution were cast for 24 h and dried under vacuum at 25 °C overnight for removing the residue solvent.

2.5 Instrumental techniques

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed on a Bruker D8 diffractometer equipped with Ni-filtered in the reflection mode. The Cu K α radiation source was operated at 40 kV and 30 mA with a scan rate of 1°/min from 1° to 40°.

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra of all samples were collected on a Perkin-Elmer Paragon 500 FT-IR spectrometer in the wavenumber range of 4000 - 400 cm^{-1} .

The isothermal crystallization behavior was studied by PerkinElmer Pyris Diamond DSC calibrated using indium. All samples were heated to 180 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere and held there for 3 min to erase the thermal history. Subsequently, the samples were rapidly cooled to the specified temperatures T_{cs} , and held at this temperature to allow the complete crystallization. The proposed T_{cs} values are selected in the range between 107 and 116 °C.

TEM images of all nanocomposites were obtained on a JEOL JEM-2010 operated at an accelerating voltage of 120 kV. The samples obtained at room temperature were ultrathin-sectioned via Leica Ultra-microtome equipped with a diamond knife.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the XRD patterns of LDH, OA-LDH and SA-LDH. It can be seen, diffraction peak of LDH at $2\theta = 10.6^\circ$ shifts to 4° and 2.8° after modification by OA and SA anion. According to Bragg equation, the d-spacing of LDH layers increase from 0.84 nm to 2.21 nm and 3.16 nm. The results demonstrate that OA and SA anions are successfully intercalated into LDH gallery and result in an enlarged interlayer distance as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1: Intercalation of modifier anion into LDH layer.

FT-IR spectra of OA-LDH, SA-LDH, LDH and modifier are shown in Figure 2. Absorption bands at 3463 cm^{-1} can be observed in OA-LDH and SA-LDH, which attributed to the O-H stretching vibration of LDH hydroxide layers. The H₂O bending vibration of the interlayer water is observed at 1638 cm^{-1} . The bands below 800 cm^{-1} are due to the lattice vibration of M-O bonds, which M is corresponding to Mg or Al [5]. The stretching vibration at 2925 cm^{-1} and 2854 cm^{-1} are belonging to -CH₂- groups of the long hydrocarbon chain in modifier [6]. The vibration band at 1558 cm^{-1} is corresponding to asymmetric stretching vibration of the COO⁻ groups [7]. In addition, a sharp peak at 1384 cm^{-1} is attributed to NO₃⁻ in LDH, however, in m-LDH, this peak is very weak. These results suggest that OA and SA anions are successfully entered the LDH gallery and substitute the original anions NO₃⁻.

Figure 1: The XRD patterns of (a) LDH, OA-LDH and (b) SA-LDH.

Figure 2: The FT-IR spectra of LDH, OA-LDH, SA-LDH, OA and SA

Figure 3 shows XRD patterns of various PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites. The diffraction peak at $2\theta = 16.1^\circ, 17.2^\circ, 20.2^\circ, 23.2^\circ$ and 25.1° are corresponding to (0 -1 1), (0 1 0), (-1 1 1), (1 0 0) and (1 -1 1) planes of PBCT, respectively. In Figure 3(a), all PBCT/OA-LDH nanocomposites show extremely weak and board diffraction peak at $2\theta = 3.2^\circ$, indicating that OA-LDH layers formed a mixed of intercalated and exfoliated conformation in nanocomposites. However, in Figure 3(b), no diffraction peak of SA-LDH appears in nanocomposites, which means a fully exfoliated of LDH layers. These results imply that the regular stacking of SA-LDH layers in nanocomposites has been destroy, due to its good compatibility with PBCT and the huge interlayer distance which allowing polymer chain intercalated easily. Conversely, the interlayer distance of OA-LDH layers were much smaller, which result in a few aggregate of LDH layers.

In order to further understand the dispersion of LDH in PBCT matrix. TEM was also investigated the morphology of 5 wt% PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites, which is shown in Figure 4. As can be seen, both OA-LDH and SA-LDH layers show well dispersion in matrix. Figure 4 (a) reveals that OA-LDH layers exist in partial intercalation formation in PBCT matrix. However, SA-LDH layers are fully exfoliated. The TEM results are consistent with the XRD results.

Figure 3: The XRD patterns of (a) PBCT/OA-LDH nanocomposites, (b) PBCT/SA-LDH nanocomposites.

Figure 4: TEM images of (a) PBCT/5wt% OA-LDH and (b) PBCT/5wt% SA-LDH nanocomposite

The effect of LDH on the crystallization behaviors of neat PBCT and PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites were investigated via DSC analysis. In order to understand the formation mechanism, isothermal crystallization kinetics was analyzed employing Avrami model. Avrami equation can be described as follows[8]:

$$1-X_t = \exp(-kt^n) \quad (1)$$

where X_t is relative degree of crystallinity at crystallization time t , k is the crystallization rate constant, and n is the Avrami exponent. Eq. (1) can be transformed into its natural logarithmic form as given in Eq. (2).

$$\ln[-\ln(1-X_t)] = \ln k + n \ln t \quad (2)$$

The value of n and k can be obtained from the slope and intercept of the plots shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6. The crystallization half-time ($t_{1/2}$) also defined in Eq. (3).

$$t_{1/2} = (\ln 2/k)^{1/n} \quad (3)$$

Figure 5 shows that all samples appear to fit very well with Avrami equation, as a straight line can be seen. This means that the crystallization behaviors of all samples are in good agreement of the Avrami model and are allowed to analyze isothermal crystallization kinetics.

The crystallization half-time ($t_{1/2}$), which is defined as the time at 50 % crystallization, can be employed to discuss the crystallization rate of materials. The $t_{1/2}$ values can be obtained from Figure 6, which shows the X_t as a function of time, for PBCT and PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites at various crystallization temperatures. The data of neat PBCT and PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites are listed in Table 1. The $t_{1/2}$ value for all samples increases with the increasing crystallization temperature (T_c), indicating that the crystallization rate decreases with increasing T_c , due to the low supercooling at higher T_c . Moreover, the $t_{1/2}$ value of PBCT/OA-LDH nanocomposites is significantly lower than that for neat PBCT and even decrease with increasing OA-LDH content, suggesting that LDH layers act as heterogeneous nucleating agents which cause an increase in the crystallization rate. Nevertheless, the $t_{1/2}$ value of nanocomposites with the SA-LDH content is the opposite to that of OA-LDH, due to the huge size of stearic anion on the LDH surface served as a barrier to hinder the diffusion and migration of PBCT chains. The n values of all nanocomposites are close to 2, suggesting that the PBCT spherulite grows with a 2-dimensional structure.

Figure 5: Avrami plots of (a) neat PBCT, (b) 1 wt% PBCT/OA-LDH, (c) 3 wt% PBCT/OA-LDH (d) 5 wt% PBCT/OA-LDH, (e) 1 wt% PBCT/SA-LDH, (f) 3 wt% PBCT/SA-LDH and (g) 5 wt% PBCT/SA-LDH nanocomposites.

Figure 6: The degree of crystallinity with time for the crystallization of (a) neat PBCT, (b) 1 wt% PBCT/OA-LDH, (c) 3 wt% PBCT/OA-LDH, (d) 5 wt% PBCT/OA-LDH, (e) 1 wt% PBCT/SA-LDH, (f) 3 wt% PBCT/SA-LDH and (d) 5 wt% PBCT/OA-LDH nanocomposites at different crystallization temperatures.

Sample	$T_c = 107^\circ\text{C}$			$T_c = 110^\circ\text{C}$			$T_c = 113^\circ\text{C}$			$T_c = 116^\circ\text{C}$		
	n	k (min ⁻ⁿ)	t _{1/2} (min)	n	k (min ⁻ⁿ)	t _{1/2} (min)	n	k (min ⁻ⁿ)	t _{1/2} (min)	n	k (min ⁻ⁿ)	t _{1/2} (min)
PBCT	2.27	3.27×10^{-1}	1.39	2.16	1.87×10^{-1}	1.84	2.06	1.13×10^{-1}	2.42	1.97	7.12×10^{-2}	3.18
PBCT/1wt% OA-LDH	2.25	1.43×10^0	0.72	2.14	7.99×10^{-1}	0.94	2.04	4.40×10^{-1}	1.25	1.98	2.35×10^{-1}	1.73
PBCT/3wt% OA-LDH	2.16	1.49×10^0	0.70	2.09	8.36×10^{-1}	0.91	2.00	4.66×10^{-1}	1.22	1.96	2.39×10^{-1}	1.72
PBCT/5wt% OA-LDH	2.18	1.72×10^0	0.66	2.12	9.38×10^{-1}	0.87	1.99	5.10×10^{-1}	1.17	1.93	2.77×10^{-1}	1.61
PBCT/1wt% SA-LDH	2.32	3.92×10^{-1}	1.28	2.29	2.36×10^{-1}	1.60	2.19	1.43×10^{-1}	2.05	2.09	9.13×10^{-2}	2.64
PBCT/3wt% SA-LDH	2.40	2.17×10^{-1}	1.62	2.32	1.20×10^{-1}	2.13	2.34	6.17×10^{-2}	2.81	2.18	3.81×10^{-2}	3.77
PBCT/5wt% SA-LDH	2.32	2.17×10^{-1}	1.65	2.28	1.19×10^{-1}	2.17	2.17	7.30×10^{-2}	2.82	2.05	4.51×10^{-2}	3.78

Table 1: The isothermal crystallization kinetics parameters of neat PBCT and PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposites at $T_c = 107\text{--}116^\circ\text{C}$.

4 CONCLUSIONS

LDH is successfully modified by octanoic acid and stearic acid using coprecipitation method. The structures of m-LDH is confirmed by XRD and FT-IR, demonstrating that the modifier anions intercalate into LDH gallery and result in an enlarge interlayer distance. A biodegradable PBCT/m-LDH nanocomposite has been prepared by solution blending. The XRD and TEM results reveal that PBCT/OA-LDH nanocomposites form partially intercalation type while SA-LDH layers are fully exfoliated in nanocomposites. The $t_{1/2}$ value of PBCT/OA-LDH nanocomposite decreases about 52 % compared to that of neat PBCT. However, the $t_{1/2}$ value of PBCT/SA-LDH nanocomposites increases from 2.64 to 3.78 minutes in the case of T_c at 116 °C. Therefore, adding OA-LDH into PBCT can enhance the crystallization rate, and adding SA-LDH will hinder it.

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